

Insulated sandwich panels – thermal performance

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Abstract

Lightweight industrial buildings is a less studied area in terms of energy efficiency. Given the great diversity of destinations for these types of buildings, it requires more thorough evaluation of their behaviour in the heat exchange with the environment. Currently, the most widely used, as walls and roofing solutions for industrial halls, are the insulated sandwich panels.

Even though it reached a high level of standardization on the use, usually thermal resistance of these panels is given in the current field, without taking into account the effect of thermal bridges. Also, in our national regulations there aren't details that study the behaviour at the heat transfer for these type of walls and roofs.

Thus, in order to improve the current design, it requires the analysis of constructive details to allow assessment of thermal bridges that occur at joints of these panels.

Thermal bridges are areas in the building envelope where the heat transfer flux increases and therefore the heat losses are higher. Their analysis requires, therefore, accurate numerical calculations.

This article, by analyzing common details of walls and roofs and by performing a two-dimensional numerical calculation of the linear coefficient of heat transfer, aims to study the thermal performance of the insulated sandwich panels.

Keywords: energy efficiency, thermal bridges, insulated sandwich panels, thermal resistance

1. Introduction

The energy efficiency of buildings, is a subject of great actuality worldwide and represent interest to a wide circle of technical specialists.

Industrial buildings have a large variety of functions involving a variable number of parameters needed for interior comfort (temperature, humidity, indoor air circulation speed, etc.)

Currently, usual constructive solutions for these type of buildings are steel structures with closure walls of insulated sandwich panels. At the moment, in the romanian scientific literature, there are no thermal bridges details, specific to these types of constructive solutions, by which it can be evaluated the energy losses through the envelope, in a way that can reflect with accurately the heat transfer with the environment.

A problematic aspect concerning energy performance evaluation of these types of constructive details, is the fact that the resistance to heat transfer is given by panel manufacturers into the field of panel and additional heat loss in the area of joints of the panels is not considered.

This article presents the results obtained by numerical simulation of heat transfer, applied to constructive details widely used in tertiary sector buildings with metal structure.

The main objective of this study is to assess the thermal performance of joints areas of metal insulated sandwich panels in order to improve knowledge of the behavior of these panels to thermal transfer.

The overall purpose is to focus the attention to this sector, less studied, in order to align current practices in Romania to EU requirements related to energy consuming buildings from the tertiary sector.

2. Thermal performance of metal insulated sandwich panels

2.1 Numerical simulation methods of heat transfer in constructive details

Evaluation of the temperature field in the construction details described in this article is made through a two-dimensional analysis (temperature varies in two directions and building elements are not homogeneous; in the third direction is a negligible temperature variation); based on a steady state heat transfer (simplifying assumption is allowed that the temperature of two environments separated by a building element does not vary in time and the heating is continuous).

Numerical simulation of two-dimensional calculation is performed using Therm program, developed by Berkeley University, California. The program incorporates a two-dimensional heat transfer model, to numerically solve Fourier's energy equation with Finite Element Method [2].

The results obtained from numerical analysis are: the corrected thermal transmittance value (U'), the temperature variation (the thermal field) into the thickness of the element and the maximum and minimum temperatures.

Through the analyzed case studies in this paper is intended to obtain values of the coefficients of linear thermal transfer, ψ that can be applied in the current design calculations to determine the corrected thermal resistance.

Based on the results obtained by numerical analysis. there are manually calculated values of the coefficients of linear thermal transfer, ψ , using the mathematical relations (1) and (2):

$$\Psi = L^{2D}_{\text{pert}} - L^{2D}_{\text{nepert}} \quad (1)$$

$$\Psi = \frac{l}{R'} - \frac{l}{R} \quad [(m^2K)/W] \quad (2)$$

where:

L^{2D} – is the thermal coupling coefficient of the element of construction, determined by a two - dimensional calculation [W/(mK)]

R – thermal resistance [(m²K)/W]

R' - corrected thermal resistance [(m²K)/W]

l - represents the length by which is calculated the value of ψ [m]

In the numerical modeling, the constructive details comply with the requirements imposed by the norm SR EN ISO 10211: 2008 and norm C107/3 - Appendix J.

2-D geometric model is obtained by sectioning with symmetrical plans the jointing area of the panels, to study the effect of thermal bridges that appears. The considered length of the section of the panel is $d_{\text{min}} = 1\text{m}$, considered on both sides of the connection [3]. The horizontal and vertical cutouts of each model, is considered adiabatic.

In the considered detail of metal insulated roof panels jointing is applied a correction of dimensions, in order to simplify the geometric model. According to SR EN ISO 10211:2008, the local correction perpendicular to the middle of the outer surface of the panels that can be applied is d_c ,

calculated with eq.(3) , where the value for R_c is considered $0.03 \text{ m}^2\text{K/W}$.

$$d_c = R_c * \lambda \quad [\text{m}] \quad (3)$$

The geometric model ranged between cutout plans, has the finite element mesh with the distance between two consecutive nodes up to 20 mm.

Boundary conditions applied to the studied geometric models are:

Temperatures:

$T_i = 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ – indoor air temperature

$T_e = -18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ – outdoor air temperature

Surface heat transfer coefficients:

$\alpha_i = 0.125 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ – interior surface heat transfer coefficient

$\alpha_e = 0.042 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ – exterior surface heat transfer coefficient

Thermal conductivity of materials [4]:

- steel, $\lambda = 58 \text{ W/mK}$

- rigid polyurethane, $\lambda = 0.024 \text{ W/mK}$, declared value; $\lambda = 0.038 \text{ W/mK}$, calculation value

- expanded polystyrene, $\lambda = 0.044 \text{ W/mK}$

- anticondensation tape, $\lambda = 0.6 \text{ W/mK}$

2.2 Case Studies

For this study, are considered two types of constructive details of metal insulated sandwich panels jointings, commonly used into the current design.

The first analysed constructive detail – Figure 1, is the connection between the roof panels, composed of metal sheet of thickness 6 mm on the outer, a layer of insulating material and a metal sheet of 6 mm thickness on the interior. In order to follow the differences in thermal losses depending on the type of insulation material chosen, were compared the linear heat transfer coefficient values obtained by considering two types of insulating materials: rigid polyurethane and expanded polystyrene. In the current field, panel thickness is 80 mm and the height of each haunch is 35 mm. For the roof panels, the metal sheet is continuous over the entire width of the panel joint area.

Figure1. Constructive detail of metal insulated sandwich roof panels jointing

Applying the local correction perpendicular to the median position of each haunch on the outer surface (d_c), it creates a the geometric model shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Geometric pattern of roof panels detail

The second constructive detail - Figure 3, is a horizontal connection between wall panels composed

of metal sheet of 6 mm thickness in outer, an insulating layer of 80 mm thickness: rigid polyurethane, respectively expanded polystyrene and a metal sheet of 6 mm thickness on the interior. For the wall panels, the metal sheet is not continuous over the width of the panel joint area. The geometric model is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 3. Constructive detail of metal insulated sandwich wall panels jointing
 Figure 4. Geometric pattern of wall panels constructive detail

3. Results and discussion

For the roof panels constructive detail, the graphical results of the numerical analysis are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6, and there are completed with numerical results shown in Table 7.

Figure 5. Isotherms of the roof panels constructive detail

Figure 6. Infrared temperature field of the roof panels constructive detail

Table 7: Numerical results for horizontal detail of metal insulated roof panels jointing

Calculation parameters		Computing wing							
		L=25 cm			L=50 cm		L=75 cm		L=100 cm
Insulation material	R_{field}	R_{cor}	Ψ	R_{cor}	Ψ	R_{cor}	Ψ	R_{cor}	Ψ
	m^2K/W	m^2K/W	W/mK	$m^2 K/W$	W/mK	$m^2 K/W$	W/mK	$m^2 K/W$	W/mK
PUR	2.272	0.870	0.177	1.249	0.180	1.472	0.179	1.614	0.179
EPS	1.985	0.833	0.174	1.166	0.177	1.354	0.176	1.471	0.176

It can be noticed a significant influence of jointing area of the panels. For a wing computing $L = 100$ cm, determined according to SR EN ISO 10211:2008, corrected thermal resistance represents about 71% of the calculated thermal resistance in the field, for roof panels with PUR as insulation material, respectively 74%, for roof panels with expanded polystyrene as insulation material. The calculated value of ψ , remains approximately constant, regardless of wing calculation considered in the numerical analysis. The maximum difference between the values of ψ is 0.003 W/mK.

For the wall panels constructive detail, the graphical results of the numerical analysis are shown in Figure 8, and there are completed with numerical results shown in Table 9.

Figure 8. Isotherms / Infrared temperature field of the wall panels constructive detail

Table 9: Numerical results for vertical detail of metal insulated wall panels jointing

Calculation parameters		Computing wing							
		L=25 cm			L=50 cm		L=75 cm		L=100 cm
Insulation material	R_{field}	R_{cor}	Ψ	R_{cor}	Ψ	R_{cor}	Ψ	R_{cor}	Ψ
	$m^2 K/W$	$m^2 K/W$	W/mK	$m^2 K/W$	W/mK	$m^2 K/W$	W/mK	$m^2 K/W$	W/mK
PUR	2.272	1.875	0.023	2.052	0.023	2.121	0.023	2.156	0.023
EPS	1.985	1.678	0.023	1.816	0.023	1.869	0.023	1.896	0.024

On a standard size panel ($L = 100$ cm), the corrected thermal resistance is about 90% of the thermal resistance calculated into the field, for PUR as insulation material, respectively 95%, for expanded polystyrene.

The calculated value of ψ , remains approximately constant, regardless of wing calculation considered in the numerical analysis. The maximum difference between the values of ψ is 0.001 W/mK.

4. Conclusions

According to the results obtained on the analysis of thermal bridges, for both types of panels, for the closure walls and for the roof, it is noticed that corrected thermal resistance decreases compared to

that declared by the manufacturer.

By varying lengths of computing wing ($L=25$ cm-100 cm), it appears that the entire panel surface is affected by thermal bridging effect of the jointing area.

For the calculated linear heat transfer coefficients, ψ , the value remains approximately constant regardless of the panel wing computing.

Regarding the characteristics of insulating material, is observed that if the insulating material has a lower thermal conductivity, the losses in the joint are higher.

It can be seen the importance of approaching the subject, given that reducing energy consumption as early as the design phase becomes a more stringent requirement worldwide, and in order to properly address the issue, it must correlate correct technical features of the products offered by manufacturers with methods of calculation used in current design.

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